

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY

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The present study aims at studying the relationship between various dimensions of emotional intelligence and occupational stress of among teachers working in secondary schools of Jalandhar and Ludhiana districts of Punjab, India. Using a multi-stage random sampling method, a sample volume of 739 teachers was determined. Two main instruments were used to measure the study variables: a 80-item questionnaire by C R Darolia on emotional intelligence (five scales: Self-awareness, Motivating Oneself, Managing Emotions, Empathy and Handling Relations, and a 60-item Occupational Role Questionnaire (six scales: Role Overload (RO), Role Insufficiency (RI), Role ambiguity (RA), Role Boundary (RB), Responsibility (R), and Physical Environment (PE)) extracted from Occupational Stress Inventory Revised (OSI-R) by Samuel H Osipow, 1998. The Pearson product moment correlation was used to establish the relationship. The study results revealed that a) Firstly, the emotional intelligence does not help in reducing the feeling of job pressures; b) Similarly being self aware, motivated and empathetic does not have any influence on the feeling of job pressure; c) teachers who are highly emotionally intelligent found to have clear understanding of the expectations from them, their priorities for job and evaluation criteria set for them. d) highly emotionally intelligent teachers are going to have less conflicting role demands and loyalties at the work setting; e) emotional intelligence is not related to taking responsibility for performance of others; f) highly emotionally intelligent teachers are less likely to perceive the settings of the schools as poor and working conditions as extreme.

INTRODUCTION

Education has been increasingly advocated as the birth right of the child. It is basic to the overall development i.e. physical, material, spiritual, social and intellectual of the child. It is the investment in the present for creating well educated workforce of the future. It is the mean of attaining self reliance and helps in contributing to the goals of values enshrined in the constitution. It helps to determine the prosperity, welfare and security of the society. Thus, the societies are increasingly focusing on the development of the human resource through the means of education. With the implementation of proper, sincere and well directed efforts, it will help in ensuring economic prosperity of the nation. The teachers if given autonomy and good working conditions are helpful in achieving the goals of national development. Their well being shall be taken care of. Also, therefore the teaching community in India, is highly respected. Though the state of teaching profession in India is no different than any developed country, it is stressful and burdened with lot of responsibilities alongwith teaching duties. Herein, the role of emotional intelligence

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is being touted as instrumental in making the success of teachers in this work environment. Though lot has been said of emotional intelligence in different work environments teaching sector has not been well researched in this part of the world.

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

Emotional Intelligence, as evident from the constituent words, is the combination of two words i.e. Emotional and Intelligence. Emotional Intelligence in layman's language means Intelligence which is concerned with Emotional aspect of one's behavior. Emotional Intelligence is Intelligence but it is very much different from general Intelligence.

Mayer and Salovey (1995) had introduced the term emotional intelligence in their attempt to develop a scientific measure for understanding the basis of difference in people's ability in the area of emotions. They defined emotional intelligence as the capacity to perceive emotions; to integrate them in thoughts, to understand them and to manage them. However, the credit of popularizing the notion of Emotional Intelligence goes to Goleman (1995). According to him emotional intelligence encompasses the following five characteristics and abilities i.e. self awareness, mood management, self motivation, empathy and managing relationship. Since then, the emotional intelligence is recognized as a construct which is thought as essential to individual's social and organisational success and as an outcome of organizations (Cooper and Sawaf, 1997; Goleman, 1998; Ryback, 1998).

Individuals and organizations with high emotional intelligence are noticeable separately as they are more productive and they endorse productivity in others. Students and teachers with high EI perform better in schools and uphold safe and comfortable environment to learn. Caruso, Mayer and Salovey (2002) concluded from their research that people with high emotional intelligence tend to prefer social work and teaching rather than enterprising occupations i.e. salesman.

To sum up, emotional intelligence is that capacity which enables individual to respond appropriately to a diversity of environmental stimuli; and present a critical edge in different spheres of work, family, social, romantic and even spiritual settings. Emotional intelligence helps to understand emotions, which are instrumental for self-awareness and self preservation that deeply connects us to ourselves and others. Goleman (1995) asserts that people who are emotionally proficient i.e. are able to know and manage their own feelings well, and have the skill to read and deal effectively with other people's feelings benefit more than others in any domain of life. They are more likely to be content and effective in day to day functioning in their lives. For example, Malek (2000) concluded that Emotional Intelligence scores and scores on collaborative conflict management style are significantly correlated to each other. Similarly, Chipain (2003) finds that Emotional Intelligence is contributes positively to sales performance. Also, when sound process practices are coupled with analytical skills and Emotional Intelligence, line managers started

contributing through improved productivity, quality, and cost that bettered the bottom line.

Highlighting the role of emotional intelligence Linn (2004), concluded that training in emotional intelligence could be a potent instrument in accomplishing planned business goals in the areas of hiring, training, and performance development. Likewise, Drago (2004) concluded that academic achievement is strongly correlated with the students' ability to recognize, use, and deal with their emotions. Wilkins (2004) further suggested that the emotional intelligence skills are linked with the retention rates among learners, thus highlighting the importance of Emotional Intelligence towards enhancing learner success through designed methods.

On the effects of emotional intelligence on the correlation between job stress and job performance Yu-Chi Wu (2011) on a sample of employees in the Taiwanese finance sector concluded that emotional intelligence had a positive impact on job performance and moderated this relationship. He outlined that highly emotionally intelligent employees are more capable of reducing or transforming the potential negative effects of job stress on job performance than the employees with low emotional intelligence.

OCCUPATIONAL STRESS

Stress carries a negative connotation by some people as it is thought to be something which shall be avoided. This is regrettable, because stress is a great asset to an individual as well as to an organization in managing legitimate emergencies and achieving peak performance (Nelson and Quick, 1994).

There is increasing concern among educators about teacher's mental health. Job related stress is an important cause in teacher's motivation and retention. Teaching once considered a routine job, became a complex profession for regular as well as special education teachers in the last decade (Fimian and Blanton, 1987). Issues such as litigation, liability, accountability to students' parents and managements, tenure, unions, along with increasingly diverse responsibilities and fast changing ideas have made teaching more stressful. Infact, as many as 20% of all new teachers leave education sector during the first few years due to the complexity of the job (Duke, 1984).

From the review of existing literature, it has been concluded that stress that there are essentially three different, but overlapping approaches to the definition and study of stress (Lazarus, 1966; Appley and Trumbull, 1967; Cox, 1978, 1990, 1993; Cox and Mackay, 1981 and Fletcher, 1988). The first approach conceptualizes occupational stress as an aversive or harmful characteristic of the work environment, wherein, it is treated as an independent variable- the environmental cause of ill health. This has been termed as the 'engineering approach'. The second approach, on the other hand, defines stress in terms of the common psychological effects of

a wide range of aversive or noxious stimuli. It treats stress as dependent variable-as particular physiological response to a threatening or damaging environment. This has been termed the 'physiological approach'. The third approach conceptualizes work stress in terms of the dynamic interaction between the person and their work environment. When studied, stress is either inferred from the existence of problematic person- environment interactions or measured in terms of the cognitive processes and emotional reactions which underpin those interactions. This final approach has been termed the 'psychological approach'.

The sources of work related stress for teachers ranged differently from one end to another and summarize the extent to which the sources are in the different aspects of responsibility a teacher undertakes in day to day routine. Hodge and Marker (1978) identified workplace related sources of stress for teachers as poor relationships with students, colleagues, and administrative staff; multifarious communication needs; inattentive students; and issues of discipline in and out of classrooms. Other factors that are mentioned are daily abuse from teachers and parents and high community standards for teacher conformity to social values (Grossnickle, 1980; Swick and Hanley, 1980; Kyriacou, 1984). Chen and Miller (1997) reported organizational characteristics and individual characteristics as the factors contributing to stress among teachers. The organizational characteristics i.e. time constraints, excessive workloads and low salaries, Insufficient classroom resources, large classes, administrative bureaucracy, little involvement in decision making, absence of collegiality and a sense of school community, problems with student discipline and classroom management, and very less opportunities for promotions or advancement. Similarly, individual characteristics include, for instance, feeling of alienation and powerlessness among younger and less experienced teachers. Pullis (1992) conducted a survey on 244 teachers of the behaviorally disordered. Based on the analysis it is found that perceived sources of stress among school/setting factors by the teachers include career issues, and workload variables as more stressful than direct contact with students. The teachers reported that emotional exhaustion, frustration, and negative carryover of stressful events to life outside the classroom were frequent effects of stress. Schonfeld (1991) conducted a study to examine the link between occupational conditions and depressive symptoms in newly appointed teachers. On the basis of investigation, he is able to conclude that teachers in the most difficult schools showed an increase in depressive symptoms and that the relationship between working conditions and depressive symptoms is strong. Teachers in the most adverse school environments exhibited the most depressive symptoms although there were no pre employment differences in the summer questionnaire.

The job of principals or administrators in the school sector are also of too much pressure and an analysis of job factors which caused administrative stress in different studies were 'people-related responsibility areas' rather than routine issues

related. Zimbabwean school administrators had reported that most sources of stress for them is people related i.e. supervising teachers, evaluating teachers, supervising extra curricular activities, poor students' results, inadequate resources, overcrowded classes, lack of parental interest in students' work, dealing with parents, and limited chances for promotion (Nhundu, 1999). Similarly, Wilson and Otto (1988) concluded that primary school administrators identify lack of autonomy and recognition, increasing workload, responsibility for others and improper resources for use are significant sources of occupational stress. Likewise, role overload and poor human resources or lack of expertise to fulfill curriculum demands are reported as sources of stress by primary head teachers (Downton, 1987). Borg and Riding (1993) also surveyed 150 Maltese public school administrators and found that about 20% viewed their job as very stressful. They concluded that those who reported greater stress levels were least satisfied with their administrator role. Four major stress factors were lack of support and conflict resolution problems, inadequate resources, workload, and work conditions and responsibilities.

Yang *et al.* (2009) found age as a significant predictor of stress among teachers. Similarly, Sun, Wu & Wang (2011) conducted study to assess the occupational stress among university teachers in China and clarify its risk factors. Eight universities (2 multidiscipline and 6 specialized) and 10% of academic staff each were randomly sampled. Chinese Version Personal Strain Questionnaire and demographic characteristics, health status, work situations, and personal and social resources were used for collection of data from 827 effective respondents. The average raw score on Personal Strain Questionnaire was 91.0 among the university teachers. General linear model analysis showed that the factors significantly associated with the Personal Strain score were, in standardized estimate ($\hat{\alpha}$) sequence, mental health, role overload, role insufficiency, social support, monthly income, role limitations due to physical problems, research finance and self-rated disease with adjustment for age and sex.

Similarly other studies pointed out that relationship between emotional intelligence and occupational stress. From the available literature it is clear that emotional intelligence helps a teacher to handle the stressful situations in different walks of life. But, in spite of this enough literature is not available on the relationship between emotional intelligence and occupational stress in this part of the world. Hence, the investigator explored through this study the relationship between emotional intelligence and occupational stress among the teachers working in secondary schools of Punjab.

Objective

The present study has been designed to study the relationship between occupational stress and emotional intelligence of teachers working in secondary schools.

Hypothesis

The study hypothesized that there exists no significant relationship between occupational stress and Emotional Intelligence scores of secondary school teachers.

Methodology

The present study used descriptive method and is co relational in nature. 30 schools comparable in terms of infrastructure, faculty and student strength each were selected randomly from two clusters i.e. Jalandhar and Ludhiana districts of Punjab. 739 secondary school teachers were selected randomly from these two clusters. Multidimensional Measures of Emotional Intelligence (MMEI) by C. R Darolia, (2003) and Occupational Role Questionnaire extracted from Occupational Stress Inventory Revised (OSI-R) by Samuel H Osipow, 1998 was administered to all these secondary school teachers. The data thus collected was put to statistical analysis.

Results

The coefficient of correlation between various dimensions of emotional intelligence and various dimensions of occupational stress among secondary school teachers have been calculated and are presented in the table 1 below.

TABLE 1: CORRELATION BETWEEN VARIOUS DIMENSIONS OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND VARIOUS DIMENSIONS OF OCCUPATIONAL STRESS

<i>Dimensions of Occupational Stress →</i>		<i>RO</i>	<i>RI</i>	<i>RA</i>	<i>RB</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>PE</i>	<i>TOS</i>
<i>Dimensions of Emotional Intelligence ↓</i>								
Self Awareness								
Sec. Schools	N=739, df= 737	-0.012	-.154**	-.236**	-.227**	-0.046	-.088*	-.214**
Govt. Schools	N=342, df= 340	-0.029	-.144**	-.261**	-.264**	-0.057	-.154**	-.274**
Pvt. Schools	N=397, df= 395	-0.011	-.161**	-.223**	-.196**	-0.052	-0.035	-.181**
High Age	N= 398, df= 396	-0.021	-.178**	-.296**	-.255**	-0.087	-.120*	-.263**
Low Age	N= 341, df= 339	-0.022	-.113*	-.158**	-.196**	-0.013	-0.058	-.159**
More Experience	N= 357, df= 355	0.011	-.170**	-.286**	-.225**	-0.061	-0.093	-.226**
Less Experience	N= 382, df= 380	-0.06	-.126*	-.187**	-.233**	-0.041	-0.089	-.205**
W/o B.Ed Qual.	N= 138, df= 136	0.057	-0.022	-0.142	-.239**	-0.087	-.189*	-.169*
Grad. With B.Ed Qual.	N= 142, df= 140	-0.09	-0.083	-.245**	-.223**	-0.054	-0.116	-.250**
PG With B.Ed Qual.	N= 459, df= 457	-0.007	-.207**	-.258**	-.227**	-0.035	-0.056	-.219**
Managing Emotions								
Sec. Schools	N=739, df= 737	-0.021	-.122**	-.115**	-.129**	-0.037	-0.051	-.132**
Govt. Schools	N=342, df= 340	-0.054	-.114*	-0.085	-.113*	-0.036	-.114*	-.155**
Pvt. Schools	N=397, df= 395	-0.007	-.127*	-.152**	-.162**	-0.062	0.001	-.134**
High Age	N= 398, df= 396	-0.002	-.117*	-.121*	-.109*	-0.051	-0.035	-.117*
Low Age	N= 341, df= 339	-0.065	-.119*	-0.1	-.160**	-0.036	-0.085	-.158**
More Experience	N= 357, df= 355	-0.007	-.120*	-.106*	-.111*	-0.052	-0.021	-.112*
Less Experience	N= 382, df= 380	-0.059	-.109*	-.115*	-.151**	-0.034	-0.091	-.156**
W/o B.Ed Qual.	N= 138, df= 136	0.082	0.012	-0.01	-0.121	-0.14	-0.013	-0.051

contd. table 1

<i>Dimensions of Occupational Stress →</i>		<i>RO</i>	<i>RI</i>	<i>RA</i>	<i>RB</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>PE</i>	<i>TOS</i>
<i>Dimensions of Emotional Intelligence ↓</i>								
Grad. With B.Ed Qual.	N= 142, df= 140	-0.048	-0.146	-0.101	-0.13	0.074	-0.108	-0.142
PG With B.Ed Qual.	N= 459, df= 457	-0.046	-.153**	-.146**	-.133**	-0.055	-0.044	-.158**
Motivating Oneself								
Sec. Schools	N=739, df= 737	0.038	-.140**	-.234**	-.241**	-0.049	-0.061	-.193**
Govt. Schools	N=342, df= 340	0.083	-.117*	-.274**	-.325**	-0.032	-0.05	-.214**
Pvt. Schools	N=397, df= 395	-0.002	-.163**	-.206**	-.153**	-0.063	-0.069	-.177**
High Age	N= 398, df= 396	0.051	-.113*	-.241**	-.282**	-0.081	-0.054	-.197**
Low Age	N= 341, df= 339	0.012	-.169**	-.225**	-.188**	-0.019	-0.077	-.192**
More Experience	N= 357, df= 355	0.093	-.111*	-.252**	-.287**	-0.09	-0.021	-.182**
Less Experience	N= 382, df= 380	-0.037	-.158**	-.216**	-.195**	-0.017	-.107*	-.206**
W/o B.Ed Qual.	N= 138, df= 136	-0.041	-0.143	-.238**	-.316**	-0.061	-0.132	-.242**
Grad. With B.Ed Qual.	N= 142, df= 140	0.012	-0.053	-.284**	-.316**	-0.145	-0.11	-.278**
PG With B.Ed Qual.	N= 459, df= 457	0.068	-.168**	-.219**	-.198**	-0.016	-0.026	-.157**
Empathy								
Sec. Schools	N=739, df= 737	0.022	-.097*	-.147**	-.082*	-0.032	-0.047	-.108**
Govt. Schools	N=342, df= 340	0.098	-.109*	-.252**	-.163**	-0.032	-0.056	-.153**
Pvt. Schools	N=397, df= 395	-0.035	-0.09	-0.081	-0.017	-0.032	-0.039	-0.079
High Age	N= 398, df= 396	0.045	-.106*	-.137**	-.111*	0.002	-0.069	-.105*
Low Age	N= 341, df= 339	0.002	-0.092	-.159**	-0.053	-0.062	-0.022	-.110*
More Experience	N= 357, df= 355	0.079	-.136*	-.165**	-0.102	0.018	-0.043	-0.096
Less Experience	N= 382, df= 380	-0.019	-0.077	-.140**	-0.065	-0.068	-0.046	-.117*
W/o B.Ed Qual.	N= 138, df= 136	0.11	0.039	-0.104	-0.159	-0.092	-0.104	-0.088
Grad. With B.Ed Qual.	N= 142, df= 140	0.141	-0.102	-.251**	-0.131	-0.051	0.09	-0.088
PG With B.Ed Qual.	N= 459, df= 457	-0.038	-.133**	-.131**	-0.046	-0.007	-0.069	-.118*
Handling Relationships								
Sec. Schools	N=739, df= 737	-0.063	-.134**	-.168**	-.140**	-0.025	-0.038	-.156**
Govt. Schools	N=342, df= 340	-0.002	-.150**	-.250**	-.180**	0.026	-0.026	-.169**
Pvt. Schools	N=397, df= 395	-.104*	-.128*	-.109*	-0.098	-0.053	-0.036	-.137**
High Age	N= 398, df= 396	-0.036	-.161**	-.208**	-.163**	-0.022	-0.035	-.168**
Low Age	N= 341, df= 339	-0.099	-0.104	-.125*	-.110*	-0.027	-0.04	-.140**
More Experience	N= 357, df= 355	-0.009	-.196**	-.239**	-.162**	-0.02	-0.04	-.179**
Less Experience	N= 382, df= 380	-.118*	-0.083	-.113*	-.119*	-0.028	-0.034	-.133**
W/o B.Ed Qual.	N= 138, df= 136	-0.071	-0.112	-.188*	-0.109	-0.073	-0.128	-.178*
Grad. With B.Ed Qual.	N= 142, df= 140	-0.121	-.173*	-0.137	-0.144	0.005	0.023	-0.158
PG With B.Ed Qual.	N= 459, df= 457	-0.054	-.142**	-.168**	-.150**	-0.026	-0.034	-.157**
Total EI								
Sec. Schools	N=739, df= 737	-0.012	-.185**	-.257**	-.237**	-0.054	-.079*	-.230**
Govt. Schools	N=342, df= 340	0.022	-.174**	-.301**	-.289**	-0.034	-.108*	-.264**
Pvt. Schools	N=397, df= 395	-0.05	-.197**	-.225**	-.182**	-0.078	-0.054	-.209**
High Age	N= 398, df= 396	0.008	-.185**	-.277**	-.257**	-0.068	-0.081	-.235**
Low Age	N= 341, df= 339	-0.054	-.182**	-.232**	-.212**	-0.047	-0.086	-.230**
More Experience	N= 357, df= 355	0.044	-.200**	-.288**	-.249**	-0.061	-0.057	-.221**
Less Experience	N= 382, df= 380	-0.089	-.165**	-.228**	-.225**	-0.053	-.109*	-.242**
W/o B.Ed Qual.	N= 138, df= 136	0.024	-0.079	-.206*	-.270**	-0.127	-0.161	-.217*
Grad. With B.Ed Qual.	N= 142, df= 140	-0.041	-.165*	-.290**	-.280**	-0.048	-0.073	-.273**
PG With B.Ed Qual.	N= 459, df= 457	-0.018	-.225**	-.261**	-.217**	-0.04	-0.062	-.227**

*Significant at the 0.05 level of confidence

**Significant at the 0.01 level of confidence

Table 1 shows the coefficient of correlation between various dimensions and total score of Emotional Intelligence and various dimensions and total score of Occupational Stress scores of secondary school teachers.

Correlation between role overload dimension of occupational stress and handling relationship dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant at the 0.05 level of confidence for sub groups i.e. private secondary schools teachers' (-.104*) and less experienced teachers' (-.118*). Meaning thereby, that among teachers working in private schools and less experienced teachers perceive that when their job demands exceed personal and workplace resources, they fail to get along with others and work in teams. Also, they are not able to interact appropriately with different people in different situations.

Correlation between Role Insufficiency dimension of Occupational Stress and self awareness dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.154**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.144**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.161**), high age teachers' (-.178**), low age teachers' (-.113*), more experienced teachers' (-.170**), less experienced teachers' (-.126*) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.207**). Meaning thereby that being self aware about one's strengths and weaknesses reduce the chances of less eligible in terms of education, skills and experience to one's job requirements. This clarifies that self-aware individuals are more likely to have more appropriate qualifications for any job. However, this is not found true for teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification which indicate less qualification to job requirement results into no understanding of the teaching duties.

Correlation between Role Insufficiency dimension of Occupational Stress and managing emotions dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.122**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.114*), private secondary schools teachers' (-.127*), high age teachers' (-.117*), low age teachers' (-.119*), more experienced teachers' (-.120*), less experienced teachers' (-.109*) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.153**). Meaning thereby, teachers who lack in their education, skills and experience required in teaching profession are going to be poor in handling their feelings and impulses. However, this is not found true for sub groups i.e. teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification which means that as they are not qualified for the profession and they will not be able to manage their emotions properly.

Correlation between Role Insufficiency dimension of Occupational Stress and motivating oneself dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total

secondary school teachers (-.140**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.117*), private secondary schools teachers' (-.163**), high age teachers' (-.113*), low age teachers' (-.169**), more experienced teachers' (-.111*), less experienced teachers' (-.158**) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.168**). Meaning thereby, teachers in general perceive that if their education, skills and experience required in teaching profession are not proper, they will not be able to set goals for achievement and will not be able to take them to their logical end. However, this is not found true for two sub groups i.e. teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification which means that they do not link their motivation to teaching skills, knowledge and experience.

Correlation between Role Insufficiency dimension of Occupational Stress and empathy dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.097*); government secondary schools teachers' (-.109*), high age teachers' (-.106*), more experienced teachers' (-.136*) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.133**). Meaning thereby that teachers perceive that with better educational knowledge and skills, they will be able to empathize better with others i.e. understanding other's feelings and perspective and help them accordingly. However, this is not found true in sub groups i.e. private school teachers, low age teachers, less experienced teachers, teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification. Teachers of these sub groups do not believe that their qualification, skills and experience does not help in understanding others and empathize with them.

Correlation between Role Insufficiency dimension of Occupational Stress and handling relationships dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.134**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.150**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.128*), high age teachers' (-.161**), more experienced teachers' (-.196**), graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.173*) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.142**). Meaning thereby that qualification, skills and experience makes one more able to work in teams and get along with others to have better relations with colleagues and friends. However, this is not found true with sub groups of teachers i.e. low age teachers, less experienced teachers and teacher without B.Ed qualification which indicate among these as they are lacking in qualification, skills and experience and do not find their utility in handling relationships with others.

Correlation between Role Insufficiency dimension of Occupational Stress and emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.185**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.174**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.197**), high age teachers' (-.185**), low age teachers' (-.182**), more

experienced teachers' (-.200**), less experienced teachers' (-.165**), graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.165*) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.225**). Meaning thereby, teachers who are high on emotional intelligence will be low on the feeling that they are not matching up with qualification, skills and experience required for the teaching job position. However, this is not found true with sub groups of teachers i.e. teacher without B.Ed qualification which indicate that they do not understand the role of qualification and skills for teaching job position in the development of positive emotional intelligence.

Correlation between Role Ambiguity dimension of Occupational Stress and self awareness dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant at the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.236**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.261**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.223**), high age teachers' (-.296**), low age teachers' (-.158**), more experienced teachers' (-.286**), less experienced teachers' (-.187**), graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.245**) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.258**). Meaning thereby, teachers, who are self aware, will also be clear about their expectations, priorities and evaluation criteria for teachers. However, this is not found true for teachers without B.Ed qualification. This might be due to the fact that untrained teachers are not having enough knowledge about the nitty gritty of the teaching job.

Correlation between Role Ambiguity dimension of Occupational Stress and managing emotions dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.115**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.152**), high age teachers' (-.121*), more experienced teachers' (-.106*) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.146**). Meaning thereby, teachers who manage their emotions well will also be clear about the expectations, priorities and evaluation criteria applicable for them. However, the same is not found true for sub groups i.e. teachers working in government schools, low age teachers, teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification. This might be due to the fact that the clarity of expectations, priorities and evaluation criteria for job comes with experience and fresh teachers or untrained teachers may not be have orientation of this aspect.

Correlation between Role Ambiguity dimension of Occupational Stress and motivating oneself dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.234**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.274**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.206**), high age teachers' (-.241*), low age teachers' (-.225**), more experienced teachers' (-.252**), less experienced teachers' (-.216**), teachers without B.Ed qualification (-.238**),

graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.284**) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.219**). Meaning thereby that the teachers who are motivated enough are clear about the expectations, priorities and evaluation criteria fixed for them.

Correlation between Role Ambiguity dimension of Occupational Stress and empathy dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.147**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.252**), high age teachers' (-.137**), low age teachers' (-.159**), more experienced teachers' (-.165**), less experienced teachers' (-.140**), graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.251**) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.131**). Meaning thereby that the empathy helps in having clarity of expectations, priorities and evaluation criteria expected. Teachers who are able to empathise will also be clear of expectations, priorities and evaluation criteria. However, this is not found true for sub groups i.e. private school teachers and teachers without B.Ed qualification. This may be due to the fact that empathy develops with age and experience.

Correlation between Role Ambiguity dimension of Occupational Stress and handling relationships dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.168**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.250**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.109*), high age teachers' (-.208**), low age teachers' (-.125**), more experienced teachers' (-.239**), less experienced teachers' (-.113*), teachers without B.Ed qualification (-.188*) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.168**). Meaning thereby that the teachers who are able to handle their relationships with colleagues, students and authorities are also clear about expectations, priorities and evaluation criteria required for the teaching job. However, this is not found true for teachers without B.Ed qualification. The reason may be that untrained teachers because of their lack of understanding of job requirements.

Correlation between Role Ambiguity dimension of Occupational Stress and emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.257**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.301**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.225**), high age teachers' (-.277**), low age teachers' (-.232**), more experienced teachers' (-.288**), less experienced teachers' (-.228**), teachers without B.Ed qualification (-.206*), graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.290**) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.261**). Meaning thereby that the teachers who are high on emotional intelligence will also have clear understanding of the expectations, priorities and evaluation criteria required for the teaching job.

Correlation between Role Boundary dimension of Occupational Stress and self awareness dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant at the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.227**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.264**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.196**), high age teachers' (-.255**), low age teachers' (-.196**), more experienced teachers' (-.225**), less experienced teachers' (-.233**), teachers without B.Ed qualification (-.239**), graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.223**) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.227**). Meaning thereby, highly self aware teachers will also have less conflicting role demands and loyalties in the work settings.

Correlation between Role Boundary dimension of Occupational Stress and managing emotions dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.129**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.113*), high age teachers' (-.162**), more experienced teachers' (-.111*), less experienced teachers' (-.151*) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.133**). Meaning thereby that the teachers who are able to handle and manage their feelings in adverse and favourable situations are also able to minimize the conflicting role demands and loyalties in the work settings. However, their relationship is not found significant for the sub groups i.e. teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification.

Correlation between Role Boundary dimension of Occupational Stress and motivating oneself dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant at the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.241**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.325**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.153**), high age teachers' (-.282**), low age teachers' (-.188**), more experienced teachers' (-.287**), less experienced teachers' (-.195**), teachers without B.Ed qualification (-.316**), graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.316**) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.198**). Meaning thereby, teachers who are motivated and know about their goals and work continuously to achieve those goals are having less conflicting role demands and loyalties in the work settings.

Correlation between Role Boundary dimension of Occupational Stress and empathy dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.082*); government secondary schools teachers' (-.163**) and high age teachers' (-.111**). Meaning thereby that the teachers, who are high on empathy skills are having less conflicting role demands and loyalties in the work setting. But this is true only for teachers working in government schools and high age teachers. This might be due to the fact that teachers in government schools are more experienced and aged.

Correlation between Role Boundary dimension of Occupational Stress and handling relationships dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.140**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.180**), high age teachers' (-.163**), low age teachers' (-.110**), more experienced teachers' (-.162**), less experienced teachers' (-.119*) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.150**). Meaning thereby, teachers who have good skills of handling and managing their relationships are having less conflicting role demands and loyalties at the work setting. However, the same is not found true with teachers working in private schools, untrained teachers and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification due to the fact that they are inexperienced and low age.

Correlation between Role Boundary dimension of Occupational Stress and emotional intelligence is found to be significant at the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.237**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.289**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.182**), high age teachers' (-.257**), low age teachers' (-.212**), more experienced teachers' (-.249**), less experienced teachers' (-.225**), teachers without B.Ed qualification (-.270**), graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.280**) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.217**). Meaning thereby teachers having high emotional intelligence are going to have less conflicting role demands and loyalties at the work setting.

Correlation between Physical Environment dimension of Occupational Stress and self awareness dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.088*); government secondary schools teachers' (-.154**), high age teachers' (-.120*) and teachers without B.Ed qualification (-.189*). Meaning thereby, teachers having high self awareness ability perceive less about the poor surroundings and extreme physical conditions in the school setting. This is found true for the teachers working in government schools, high age teachers and trained teachers. This shows that old teachers who had seen change in school setting are able to cope with them. Similarly those who are on the job without adequate qualification are able to cope up because of their need.

Correlation between Physical Environment dimension of Occupational Stress and managing emotions dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant at the 0.05 level of confidence for the sub group i.e. government secondary schools teachers' (-.114*). Meaning thereby that the teachers working in government schools who score high on handling emotions are less likely to perceive the work setting of schools as poor and working conditions as extreme. However, for other groups the relationship is not found significant which signals towards the poor working conditions and torturous settings.

Correlation between Physical Environment dimension of Occupational Stress and motivating oneself dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant at the 0.05 level of confidence only for the sub group i.e. Less experienced teachers' (-.107*). Meaning thereby, the ability of motivating oneself is not related to perceiving poor working conditions and extreme facilities. However, less experienced teachers with high ability of motivating oneself perceive conditions of working as less extreme.

Correlation between Physical Environment dimension of Occupational Stress and emotional intelligence is found to be significant at the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.079*); government secondary schools teachers' (-.108*) and less experienced teachers' (-.109*). Meaning thereby, teachers' in general with high emotional intelligence are less likely to perceive the settings of the schools as poor and working conditions as extreme. Specifically government schools teachers and less experienced teachers are found to be like that.

Correlation between Total Occupational Stress and self awareness dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.214**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.274**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.181**), high age teachers' (-.263**), low age teachers' (-.159**), more experienced teachers' (-.226**), less experienced teachers' (-.205**), teachers without B.Ed qualification (-.169*), graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.250**) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.219**). Meaning thereby that highly stressed teachers will have less self awareness about themselves and vice versa.

Correlation between Total Occupational Stress and managing emotions dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.132**), government secondary schools teachers' (-.155**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.134**), high age teachers' (-.117*), low age teachers' (-.158**), more experienced teachers' (-.112*), less experienced teachers' (-.156**) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.158**). Meaning thereby that the highly stressed teachers will have less ability to handle and manage their emotions and vice versa. However, this is not found true with untrained teachers and teachers with B.Ed qualification, which indicates that occupational stress and managing emotions have no relationship for these sub groups. This indicates to either lack of understanding of teachers' job requirement.

Correlation between Total Occupational Stress and motivating oneself dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant at the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.193**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.214**), private secondary schools

teachers' (-.177**), high age teachers' (-.197**), low age teachers' (-.192**), more experienced teachers' (-.182**), less experienced teachers' (-.206**), teachers without B.Ed qualification (-.242**), graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.278**) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.157**). Meaning thereby, highly stressed teachers will not be able to motivate themselves to achieve goals in their job positions and vice versa.

Correlation between Total Occupational Stress and empathy dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.108**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.153**), high age teachers' (-.105*), low age teachers' (-.110*), less experienced teachers' (-.117*), and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.118*). Meaning thereby, highly stressed teachers will have less ability of empathy and vice versa. However, the same is not found true for teachers working in private schools, teachers without B.Ed qualification, teachers with B.Ed qualification and more experienced teachers. This indicates that the private institutions, experience and training do not facilitate the negative relationship between total occupational stress and empathy dimension of emotional intelligence.

Correlation between Total Occupational Stress and handling relationships dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant either at the 0.05 or the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.156**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.169**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.137**), high age teachers' (-.168**), low age teachers' (-.140**), more experienced teachers' (-.179**), less experienced teachers' (-.133**), teachers without B.Ed qualification (-.178*) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.157**). Meaning thereby, highly stressed teachers will have less ability to handle relationships with their colleagues, students and authorities. However, the same is not found true with graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification.

Correlation between Total Occupational Stress and emotional intelligence is found to be significant at the 0.01 level of confidence for the sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers (-.230**); government secondary schools teachers' (-.264**), private secondary schools teachers' (-.209**), high age teachers' (-.235**), low age teachers' (-.230**), more experienced teachers' (-.221**), less experienced teachers' (-.242**), teachers without B.Ed qualification (-.217**), graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.273**) and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification (-.227**). Meaning thereby, highly stressed teachers will have less emotional intelligence ability and vice versa.

Hence, significant correlation is found between various dimensions of Occupational Stress and various dimensions of Emotional Intelligence for teachers. Thus, the hypothesis, 'There exists no significant relationship between various dimensions of Occupational Stress and various dimensions of Emotional Intelligence scores of secondary school teachers' is rejected for various sub groups

except for (a) role overload dimension of occupational stress and self awareness dimension of emotional intelligence for all sub groups; role overload dimension of occupational stress and managing emotions dimension of emotional intelligence for all sub groups; role overload dimension of occupational stress and motivating oneself dimension of emotional intelligence for all sub groups; role overload dimension of occupational stress and empathy dimension of emotional intelligence for all sub groups; role overload dimension of occupational stress and emotional intelligence; role overload dimension of occupational stress and handling relationship dimension of emotional intelligence for sub groups i.e. total secondary school teachers; government secondary schools teachers', high age teachers', low age teachers', more experienced teachers', graduate teachers without B.Ed qualification; graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification, (b) role insufficiency dimension of occupational stress and self awareness dimension of emotional intelligence for sub groups i.e. teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; role insufficiency dimension of occupational stress and managing emotions dimension of emotional intelligence for sub groups i.e. teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; role insufficiency dimension of occupational stress and motivating oneself dimension of emotional intelligence for sub groups i.e. teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; role insufficiency dimension of occupational stress and empathy dimension of emotional intelligence for sub groups i.e. private school teachers, low age teachers, less experienced teachers, teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; role insufficiency dimension of occupational stress and handling relationship dimension of emotional intelligence for sub groups i.e. low age teachers, less experienced teachers and teacher without B.Ed qualification; role insufficiency dimension of occupational stress and emotional intelligence for sub group i.e. teacher without B.Ed qualification; (c) role ambiguity dimension of occupational stress and self awareness dimension of emotional intelligence for sub groups i.e. teachers without B.Ed qualification; role ambiguity dimension of occupational stress and managing emotions dimension of emotional intelligence for sub groups i.e. teachers working in government schools, low age teachers, teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; role ambiguity dimension of occupational stress and empathy dimension of emotional intelligence for sub groups i.e. private school teachers and teachers without B.Ed qualification; role ambiguity dimension of occupational stress and handling relationship dimension of emotional intelligence for sub groups i.e. teachers without B.Ed qualification; (d) Role Boundary dimension of Occupational Stress and managing emotions dimension of emotional intelligence for the sub groups i.e. teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; Role Boundary dimension of Occupational Stress and

empathy dimension of emotional intelligence for sub groups i.e. private secondary schools teachers', low age teachers', more experienced teachers', less experienced teachers'; graduate teachers without B.Ed qualification; graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; Role Boundary dimension of Occupational Stress and handling relationships dimension of emotional intelligence for the sub groups i.e. teachers working in private schools, untrained teachers and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; (e) Responsibility dimension of occupational stress and various dimensions of emotional intelligence for all of the sub groups; (f) Physical Environment dimension of Occupational Stress and self awareness dimension of emotional intelligence for the sub groups i.e. private secondary schools teachers', low age teachers', more experienced teachers', less experienced teachers', graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; Physical Environment dimension of Occupational Stress and managing emotions dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant at the 0.05 level of confidence for the sub group i.e. total secondary school teachers, private secondary schools teachers', high age teachers', low age teachers', more experienced teachers', less experienced teachers', teachers without B.Ed qualification, graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; Physical Environment dimension of Occupational Stress and motivating oneself dimension of emotional intelligence is found to be significant at the 0.05 level of confidence only for the sub group i.e. total secondary school teachers, government secondary schools teachers', private secondary schools teachers', high age teachers', low age teachers', more experienced teachers', teachers without B.Ed qualification, graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; Physical Environment dimension of Occupational Stress and empathy dimension of emotional intelligence for all of the sub groups; Physical Environment dimension of Occupational Stress and handling relationships dimension of emotional intelligence for all of the sub groups; Physical Environment dimension of Occupational Stress and emotional intelligence for the sub groups i.e. private secondary schools teachers', high age teachers', low age teachers', more experienced teachers', teachers without B.Ed qualification, graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification and postgraduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; and (g) Total Occupational Stress and managing emotions dimension of emotional intelligence for the sub groups i.e. teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; Total Occupational Stress and empathy dimension of emotional intelligence for the sub groups i.e. private secondary schools teachers', more experienced teachers', teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification; total Occupational Stress and handling relationships dimension of emotional intelligence for the sub group i.e. graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification.

DISCUSSION ON RESULTS

From the results, it can be concluded that the correlation between Occupational Stress and Emotional Intelligence is found to be negative, which means that more an individual is occupationally stressed, the less are the chances that he will be emotionally intelligent (**Darvish & Nasrollahi, 2014**). Similarly, the various dimensions of occupational stress are found to be correlated with various dimensions of emotional intelligence. The highly stressed teachers will have less self awareness about themselves and vice versa. Similarly, the highly stressed teachers will have less ability to handle and manage their emotions and vice versa except teachers without B.Ed qualification and teachers with B.Ed qualification. This has been advocated by **Atwater and Yammarino (1992); Atwater et al. (1998); Moshavi et al. (2003); Young and Dulewicz (2007)** who argued that self-awareness leads to improved performance. These teachers indicate their lack of understanding of teachers' job requirement. In addition, the highly stressed teachers will not be able to motivate themselves to achieve goals in their job positions and vice versa. Though motivation plays an important role in enhancing employee satisfaction and retention (**Ramlall, 2004**), if the stress level is to high employees will spend more time coping with stress then performing (**Allen, Hitt and Greer, 1982**). This indicates that teaching job is not motivating enough for accomplishment as no achievement targets seem to be in focus. This is supported by **Abdel Halim (1978)** who concluded that employees cope with stress depends on the enrichment level of the jobs they have and those on high-enriched jobs are able to direct stress into performance. Besides this, highly stressed teachers will have less ability of empathy and vice versa. This is found true with **SISSA (International School for Advanced Studies)** study that stressed males tend to become more self-centered and less able to distinguish their own emotions and intentions from those of other people. However, for women the exact opposite is true. The support and concern is an intervening link between stressful life events (**Kessler and McLeod, 1984**). However, the teachers working in private schools, teachers without B.Ed qualification, teachers with B.Ed qualification and more experienced teachers reported no relationship which indicates that the private institutions, experience and training do not facilitate the negative relationship between total occupational stress and empathy dimension of emotional intelligence. This indicates that these groups do not suffer from more stress. Also, the highly stressed teachers will have less ability to handle relationships with their colleagues, students and authorities except for graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification. This might be due to less number of friends at their level. It is also argued that social support, both within the work settings, i.e. help from colleagues or supervisors, and outside the work settings, i.e. help from friends or families, can buffer the impact of occupational stress (**House, 1981; Jayaratne et al., 1988; Cummings, 1990**). Those having good relationships are able to mitigate the negative effects of even high- stress jobs.

Firstly, the emotional intelligence does not help in reducing the feeling of job pressures. This is similar to finding by **Darvish & Nasrollahi (2011)** who reported inverse relationship between occupational stress and emotional intelligence. **Darvish & Nasrollahi (2011)** also reported that emotional control, Understanding others emotions, Emotional decision making, Cognition & expressing Emotion, Emotional management are negatively related to occupational stress. Similarly being self aware, motivated and empathetic does not have any influence on the feeling of job pressure. Contrarily, the teachers working in private schools and less experienced teachers reported that when their job demands exceed personal and workplace resources, they fail to get along with others and work in teams. Also, they are not able to interact appropriately with different people in different situations. **Mendelson et al (2000)** also reported that employees with higher role overload, but lower levels of organizational support were more likely to report that they had been adversely affected by their place of work.

Secondly, highly emotionally intelligent teachers always opined qualification, skills and experience important and continuously update their qualification and avoid situations wherein, their education and skills are not properly fit into the work profile. In other words, higher education and skills develops emotional intelligence required for the teaching job position. The finding is reflected similarly by **Culbreth et al. (2005)** who reported that employees who believe that their job matched their initial perceptions, and they were adequately trained, and peer supervision was available found themselves with reduced role stress. However, this is not found true with sub groups of teachers i.e. teacher without B.Ed qualification which indicate that they do not understand the role of qualification and skills for teaching job position in the development of positive emotional intelligence. Similarly, the different dimensions also indicated to the same belief. Self-awareness positively influences the individuals' decisions to have more appropriate qualifications among teachers w.r.t. type of institution, age and experience. This has been verified in previous studies of **Carver & Scheier (1981)**; **Duval, Silvia & Lalwani (2001)**; **Gibbons (1990)**; **Wicklund (1975)**; **Wicklund & Eckert (1992)** that self awareness enables the person to increase his/her efforts to bring behavior into line with the salient standard. Also, it brings the person into a self evaluative mode (**Ickes, Wicklund, & Ferris, 1973**).

But groupings based on qualification suggested that trained postgraduates reported similarly for self awareness ability influencing the decision for appropriate qualification, however, untrained teachers and trained graduate teachers had not reported contrarily which points out to their belief that further training in the form of refresher and orientation courses, workshops and faculty development programmes do not contribute to fulfilling teaching duties effectively or improving efficiency. Also, the teachers working in different type of institutions, different ages and different teaching experience understand that those who are not equipped

with proper knowledge and skills will be poor in handling their feelings and impulses. However, teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification differ in opinion and are of the view that proper knowledge and skills will not help in managing their emotions properly. Similarly, the teachers working in different type of institutions, different ages and different teaching experience in general perceive that higher knowledge and skills in the field of work help in chalking out goals for achievement. Here also, teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification differ and contend that teaching skills, knowledge and experience do not contribute for motivation for achievement. Also, the Private school teachers, low age teachers, less experienced teachers, teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification do not agree that better qualification, skills and experience help in understanding others and empathize with others. However, the teachers in general, government school teachers, high age teachers, more experienced teachers, post graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification perceive that better educational knowledge and skills, enhances one's skill to empathise better with others in terms of understanding their feelings and perspective and help them accordingly. The finding is similar to **Darvish & Nasrollahi (2011)** also reported that Understanding others emotions is negatively related to occupational stress. Also, being more qualified and skilled makes one a better team worker and develops better relations with colleagues and friends. But, low age teachers, less experienced teachers and teacher without B.Ed qualification reported contrarily, that being lacking in qualification, skills and experience and they are not able to appreciate the importance of acquiring more qualifications and enhancing skills for efficiency.

Thirdly, teachers who are highly emotionally intelligent found to have clear understanding of the expectations from them, their priorities for job and evaluation criteria set for them. Similar to the finding, **Behrman and Perreault (1984); Fisher and Gitelson (1983)** found a significant negative relationship between role ambiguity and performance.

Similarly, the dimensions of emotional intelligence also pointed to the same i.e. teachers who are highly self aware, are also clear about the expectations from them, their priorities for job and evaluation criteria set for them. Self-awareness is found to be critical to perform effectively (**Caldwell and O'Reilly 1982; Spiro and Weitz 1990**). However, the teachers without B.Ed qualification do not shared similar belief. This might be due to the fact that these teachers are not having enough understanding about the foundational knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

Also, the teachers who manage their emotions well are also clear about the expectations from them, their priorities for job and evaluation criteria set for them. Also, **Damasio (1994)** in his work highlighted that emotions and emotional management may be critical to effective management in general. Similarly,

Matthews et al. (2002) summarized that the success of an organisation depends in part on the ability of employees to manage their own behaviour, so that each individual can maximise their capabilities. However, the teachers working in government schools, low age teachers, teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification reported contrarily. This might be due to the fact that the clarity of expectations, priorities and evaluation criteria for job comes with experience and fresh teachers or untrained teachers may not have orientation of this aspect. The frequent postings and extra duties from government departments must be the reason for government school teachers. Motivated teachers are also clear about the expectations from them, their priorities for job and evaluation criteria set for them. Empathy skills help in having clarity of expectations, priorities and evaluation criteria expected. **The Finding is in line with Darvish & Nasrollahi (2011)**. However, private school teachers and teachers without B.Ed qualification are exception to this which might be due to the fact that empathy develops with age and experience. Teachers who are able to handle their relationships with colleagues, students and authorities are also clear about expectations, priorities and evaluation criteria required for the teaching job. However, the teachers without B.Ed qualification contradict to others. The reason may be due to the fact that they lack understanding of job requirements.

Fourthly, highly emotionally intelligent teachers are going to have less conflicting role demands and loyalties at the work setting. The finding is similar to the finding by **Burke, Greenglass, & Schwarzer (1996)**. Dimension wise also, the results indicate the same trend. Highly self aware teachers will also have less conflicting role demands and loyalties in the work settings. Similar opinion has been put forward i.e. self-awareness is critical to adapt behaviors to the specific needs (**Halln, Johanson and Seyed-Mohamed 1991; Weitz, Sujan and Sujan 1986**). Also, teachers who are able to handle and manage their feelings in adverse and favourable situations are also able to minimize the conflicting role demands and loyalties in the work settings. **Sharma & Sehwat (2014)** also found that self management is related to conflict resolution in a positive way. However, the teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification did not believe that managing feelings in adverse and favourable situations help in minimizing the conflicting role demands and loyalties at the work settings. Besides, motivated teachers who are aware of their goals and work continuously to achieve those goals are having less conflicting role demands and loyalties in the work settings. This is in tune with **Sharma & Sehwat (2014)**, who found that emotional intelligence is related to conflict resolution. Additionally, the teachers working in government schools and high age teachers who are high on empathy skills are having less conflicting role demands and loyalties in the work setting. The finding is in line with **Sharma & Sehwat (2014)**. This might be due to the fact that teachers in government schools are more experienced and aged. Conversely, the

other teachers do not agree that empathy skills help in having less conflicting role demands and loyalties in the work setting. Furthermore, the teachers who handle and manage their relationships well are having less conflicting role demands and loyalties at the work setting. However, the same is not found true with teachers working in private schools, teachers without B.Ed qualification and graduate teachers with B.Ed qualification due to the fact that they are inexperienced and low age.

Fifthly, emotional intelligence is not related to taking responsibility for performance of others. This is due to the fact that responsibility is an important potential stressor (**Cartwright & Cooper, 1997**). Similarly the different dimensions also confirmed the same. Self awareness ability is not related to feeling responsibility for performance of others. Also, the managing emotions, motivating oneself, handling relationships, empathy abilities are not related to the feeling of responsibility for performance of others.

Sixthly, highly emotionally intelligent teachers are less likely to perceive the settings of the schools as poor and working conditions as extreme. Specifically government schools teachers and less experienced teachers are found to be like that. For other groups the relationship is not significant. Similar findings are found for various dimensions of emotional intelligence. Teachers having high self awareness ability perceive less about the poor surroundings and extreme physical conditions in the school setting. Specifically, the teachers working in government schools, high age teachers and trained teachers confirmed this. The reason may be that old teachers who had seen change in school setting are able to cope with them. Similarly, those who are on the job without any adequate qualification are able to cope up because of their need. Also, the teachers working in government schools who score high on handling emotions are less likely to perceive the work setting of schools as poor and working conditions as extreme. Contrarily, the rest of teachers' groups had not reported similarly. Additionally, the ability of motivating oneself is not related to perceiving poor working conditions and extreme facilities except the less experienced teachers. They significantly agree that motivation helps in perceive conditions of working as less extreme. Besides, the empathy skills are not related to perceiving poor working conditions and extreme facilities. Similarly, the handling relationships skills are not related to perceiving poor working conditions and extreme facilities.

In other words, it can be concluded that emotional intelligence helps in reducing the occupational stress of the teachers. Also, **Cooper et al. (2011)** concluded that people with high emotional intelligence are more successful in reaching their goals.

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